

REPORT
REGIONAL COMPARISON OF ABSOLUTE GRAVIMETERS
WETTZELL-COMPARISON OF ABSOLUTE GRAVIMETERS 2021
WET-CAG2021

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1. Introduction

The Regional Comparison of Absolute Gravimeters WET-CAG2021, organized as Additional Comparison (CCM, 2015), was held in Germany at the Geodetic Observatory Wettzell (GOW) of the German Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) close to the city of Bad Kötzing in autumn 2021. All measurements were collected between September 7 and December 2, 2021.

The number of participants and the measurement schedule at GOW could not be fixed in advance due to the pandemic situation. Finally, 9 absolute gravimeters have been measuring in 5 sessions, each with one to four participating instruments.

Dr. Reinhard Falk, Dr. Axel Rülke, and Dr. Thomas Klügel (all of BKG) were in charge of the local organization. The results of the comparison were calculated independently by Dr. Hartmut Wziontek and Dr. Reinhard Falk, (BKG) and Dr. Vojtech Pálinkáš and Miloš Val'ko (VÚGTK/RIGTC).

This Additional Comparison is not registered as a metrological project. Two processing strategies were followed as described in Pálinkáš et al., 2021. In one solution, labelled as ICN, all compatible gravimeters contribute to the reference values based on their harmonized uncertainties. In the other solution, labelled as KCN, the absolute level of the comparison reference values is determined only by gravimeters belonging to NMI/DIs while all other instruments stabilize the solution with gravity differences. Solution KCN is linked to the key comparison EURAMET.M.G-K3 held 2018 also at Wettzell (Falk et al, 2020). Although WET-CAG2021 is not a key comparison, this alternative approach is followed to demonstrate the impact on the mean comparison level.

The first KCN-solution of WET-CAG2021 is linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3 by absolute gravimeter FG5-242 and indirectly by FG5X-251H considering the bias to FG5-215H and so implicitly also to CCM.G-K2.2017 comparison (Wu et al. 2020). The second version of KCN solution is using the link to CCM.G-K2.2017 comparison provided by FG5-215H and FG5-242 and will be also presented in this report.

Six instruments have also participated at EURAMET.M.G-K3 and its accompanying additional comparison WET-CAG2021 was conducted to ensure the compatibility of absolute gravimeters used for the realization of the International Terrestrial Gravity Reference System (Wziontek et al. 2021), to check the long-term stability of the FG5/X gravimeters and to evaluate two new Quantum Gravimeters. The results will also be published in the International Database for Absolute Gravity measurements AGrav (Wziontek et al. 2012).

Here we present the list of the participants and the measurements (absolute gravity values and their uncertainties) as submitted by the operators. The analysis strategy is briefly discussed and the results of the data harmonization is documented.

Finally, the results of the adjustment for both solutions are presented including the degrees of equivalence (*DoE*) of each gravimeter and the comparison reference values (CRV).

To distinguish that this additional comparison is a geodetic comparison, the uncertainties were all shown always with $k = 1$ as is usual in Geodesy.

The standard uncertainty is denoted u ($k = 1$). Sigma (σ) is denoted the standard deviation, but sometimes it also refers to standard error of estimates from least-squares adjustment.

In this report, the microGal (μGal) is used as a unit of acceleration, $1 \mu\text{Gal}$ is equal to $1 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m/s}^2$.

2. List of participants

The list of the participants is presented in Table 1. In total, 9 absolute gravimeters of 4 different types were compared. Overall, 2 teams from National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) or Designated Institutes (DIs) and 7 teams from non-NMI/DIs participated in WET-CAG2021.

Table 1. Participants in the comparison (NMI = National Metrology Institute; DI = Designated Institute). The metrological institutes taking part at WET-CAG2021 are in yellow.

Country	Institution	Gravimeter	NMI or DI	EURAMET.M.G-K3	Operator(s)
Austria	Bundesamt für Eich und Vermessungswesen (BEV), Vienna	FG5-242	YES	YES	Christian Ullrich, Barbara Zehetmaier, Andreas Hellerschmied
Czech Republic	VÚGTK/ RIGTC, Geodetic Observatory Pecný	FG5X-251HS5 ¹⁾	YES	NO, (YES, because results in KCN solution will be given in the level of FG5-215H)	Vojtech Pálinkáš, Jakub Kostelecký
Germany	Federal Agency of Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) Frankfurt/Leipzig	AQG-A02	NO	NO	Julian Glässel
Germany	GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences	AQG-B02	NO	NO	Marvin Reich, Heiko Thoss
Germany	Federal Agency of Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) Frankfurt/Leipzig	FG5-101	NO	YES	Reinhard Falk
Germany	Federal Agency of Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) Frankfurt/Leipzig	FG5-301	NO	YES	Reinhard Falk, Axel Rülke
Germany	Leibniz Universität Hannover	FG5X-220	NO	YES	Ludger Timmen
Italy	Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI) / e-geos, Matera	FG5-218	NO	YES	Domenico Iacovone, Alessandro Valluzzi
Sweden	Lantmäteriet Gävle	FG5X-233	NO	YES	Andreas Engfeldt

¹⁾ In this report we will use in the following as instrument name the short form FG5X-251H

3. Station description

The comparison was held in the New Gravity Laboratory at the Geodetic Observatory Wettzell (GOW) of the German Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) close to the city of Bad Kötzing, situated in the Bavarian Forest in Southeast of Germany. The laboratory is located far from sources of anthropogenic noise (e.g. traffic). All measurements were performed on 4 separate pillars (sites) with size of 1.2 m x 1.2 m x 1.7 m (Figure 1). The site coordinates are 49.14483° North, 12.87631° East (ETRS 89) and the elevation is 606.57 m.

Figure 1. Sketch of the New Gravity Laboratory at Geodetic Observatory Wettzell. The pillar G is occupied by the SG030 and for AG measurements the central room is equipped with 4 pillars. The pillar H was not included in the comparison, but was partly occupied by AQQ-A02 in October/November 2021. The surface centre of each pillar is marked by a small brass benchmark, indicating the position A at each pillar.

Vertical Gravity Gradients (VGGs) were determined before and during EURAMET.M.G-K3 comparison in 2018 (Falk, et.al, 2020) and exclusively these values are used for WET-CAG2021.

Table 2. Vertical gravity gradients at the 4 sites used for the comparison (Falk et.al, 2020).

Site	VGG / $\mu\text{Gal m}^{-1}$	u_{VGG} / $\mu\text{Gal m}^{-1}$
CA	-328.7	1.2
DA	-330.1	1.1
EA	-319.5	0.9
FA	-319.9	0.9

The tidal parameters (Table 3) are the same as in previous comparisons and were estimated from 10 years of continuous measurements of the superconducting gravimeter GWR SG-029 (2000-2010) installed at the Old Gravity Laboratory of GOW, at a distance of about 215 m away from the New Gravity Laboratory.

Table 3. Simplified model of tidal parameters for Wettzell derived from 10 years of continuous observation with the superconducting gravimeter SG-029.

Wave	Start freq. /cpd	End freq. /cpd	Amplitude factor	Phase lag /deg
M0+S0	0.000000	0.000010	1.00000	0.00000
SA	0.000011	0.003426	1.16000	0.00000
SSA	0.004709	0.010952	1.16000	0.00000
Mm	0.025812	0.044652	1.16448	-0.22820
Mf	0.060132	0.080797	1.14607	0.54690
Mtm	0.096423	0.249951	1.14570	0.40950
Q1	0.721500	0.906315	1.14617	-0.16000
O1	0.921941	0.940487	1.14852	0.12220
M1	0.958086	0.974188	1.15165	0.20040
P1	0.989049	0.998028	1.14896	0.16850
S1	0.999853	1.000147	1.12175	2.99680
K1	1.001825	1.003651	1.13560	0.22390
Psi1	1.005329	1.005623	1.25164	0.91950
Phi1	1.007595	1.013689	1.16481	-0.18350
J1	1.028550	1.044800	1.15572	0.10940
Oo1	1.064841	1.216397	1.15299	0.17630
2N2	1.719381	1.872142	1.16034	2.14020
N2	1.888387	1.906462	1.17625	1.93910
M2	1.923766	1.942753	1.18426	1.43640
L2	1.958233	1.976926	1.17887	0.84120
S2	1.991787	2.002885	1.18395	0.34170
K2	2.004710	2.182843	1.18466	0.53710
M3	2.753244	3.081254	1.06924	0.39180
M4	3.791964	3.937897	0.25996	48.32660

4. Absolute gravity measurements

The reported 43 measurements of the absolute gravimeters participating in WET-CAG2021 are listed in Table 4. Each gravimeter measured at least at two, in general three different sites. But some gravimeters occupied the same site several times.

The reported time of the measurement is the average of the times of the individual observations contributing to the measurement. The submitted absolute gravity measurement g_{raw} is the mean free-fall acceleration at the individual specific measurement height which has been corrected for:

- the Earth and ocean tides, referred to the zero-tide system,
- the effect of atmospheric mass variations using the local measured air pressure record and an admittance factor of $-0.3 \mu\text{Gal/hPa}$, and the reference air pressure based on the DIN5450 (ISO 2533:1975) standard atmosphere,
- the polar motion effect, estimated from the coordinates of the Celestial Ephemeris Pole relative to the IERS Reference Pole,
- vertical gravity changes above the measurement site to obtain gravity at the specified measurement height,
- known instrumental effects (e.g. speed-of light correction, self-attraction, laser beam diffraction).

The above corrections are compatible with the IGRS Conventions 2020 (Wziontek et al., 2021).

The operators were responsible for processing their gravity data and have submitted the final gravity values and uncertainties for all measured sites. The values g_{raw} were reported at the required measurement height using the VGGs given in the Table 4.

Final gradients (from Table 2) were used for transferring the values from the instrumental effective height (Wziontek et al, 2021) to the comparison height of 1.250 m. The height was chosen to minimize the contribution of uncertainty from VGGs to the uncertainty of CRV.

Residual temporal gravity variations have been considered by applying corrections based on the record of the superconducting gravimeter shown in Figure 2. Thus, the geophysical corrections (SGC, see Table 4) were computed as the negative value of the gravity residuals averaged over the period of the particular measurements. The uncertainty of such a correction in the time of the AG measurements was estimated to be maximum $0.3 \mu\text{Gal}$ and are given in table 4 also.

The final values g at the comparison height of 1.250 m together with associated uncertainties u are listed in Table 4. All reported measurements in WET-CAG2021 related to only one setup direction of a particular gravimeter, referred by operators as the "North" direction. In earlier comparisons the reported g -value was sometimes the mean value from measurements in North- and South direction of one gravimeter at the site.

Remark to treatment of reported multiple measurements at the same site for FG5-242

For several instruments multiple measurements were reported. After removing remaining temporal gravity variations (geophysical correction) for both measurements of FG5-242 on DA, no significant difference was found between the final gravity values. It was decided to use only the second measurement (less affected by sudden gravity changes due to heavy rain) because no independent setup was done. For the quantum gravimeters multiple measurements at one site with different results (Tab. 4) were used.

Correlation between observations of the same instrument.

Following Pálinkáš et al. (2021) we used the correlation coefficient of 0.75 to account for correlations of repeated observations of the same instrument, reflecting the typical ratio between repeatability and uncertainty for all gravimeters included in this comparison. The respective covariances for a particular AG "i" are then obtained from the harmonized uncertainties u_{ij} as $\text{cov} = 0.75 u_{ij, \min}^2$, where $u_{ij, \min}$ is the minimum of all u_{ij} . This approach can be understood as if the measurements of a particular gravimeter carried out within a few days are affected by the same systematic errors. So multiple measuring results of one instrument at one site after a new independent setup can be included and will provide more precise information about the instruments repeatability.

Table 4. List of the reported absolute gravity measurements during WET-CAG2021. The constant value 980,836,900.00 μGal is subtracted from all gravity values.

g_{raw} : reported gravity data with standard uncertainty u_{raw} declared by the participants, g_{raw} are corrected for all the known geophysical (tides, atmosphere, polar motion and the vertical gravity gradient) as well as instrumental effects (speed-of light correction, laser beam diffraction **DC**, self-attraction **SAC**, etc.), g_{raw} are reported at the individual measurement height **H** above the pillar using gradient **VGG**.

dg_{ref} : gravity difference between reported height of raw gravity data and 1.250 m. * The reported measurement height slightly deviates from the usual effective instrumental height. To compute the transfer correction dg_{ref} , the default effective height of FG5 and FG5X of 1.22 m or 1.27 m, respectively was used with **VGG**.

g : gravity values transferred to the reference height of the comparison (125 cm) using final gradients **VGG** and corrected for gravity variations **SGC** based on the record of the superconducting gravimeter.

u : the standard uncertainty of g computed as root mean square of three components: the declared uncertainty of the raw gravity data by the participants u_{raw} , the transfer error to the reference height of the comparison of 1.25 m. The variability of the SG based corrections (SGC) is given by σ_{SGC} . The uncertainty of this correction was assumed with 0.2 μGal .

Remark to FG5-242: After applying the geophysical correction for both measurements of FG5-242 on DA we found no significant difference between the corrected gravity values. We have decided to use the second measurement only because of a more stable geophysical correction.

Remark to FG5X-251H*: "H" is related to the modified measurement and evaluation system HS5 of the FG5X-251 gravimeter. The measurements of this gravimeter were additionally corrected for: Coriolis 0.62 μgal , Verticality 0.02 μgal , Cable -0.32 μgal , FG5 -0.32 μgal and -0.44 μgal respectively and a bias of (1.80 ± 0.3) μgal to FG5-215H, which participated at CCM.G.K2.2017. For solution ICN this bias to FG5-215H has been removed again, the device is then referred to as the FG5X-251H.

Remark to FG5-101: The measurements of this gravimeter were additionally corrected with in sum -0,34 μGal for: Coriolis 0.25 μgal , Verticality 0.22 μgal , Cable -0.48 μgal and fringe size correction: -0.33 μGal .

Remark to FG5-301: The measurements of this gravimeter were additionally corrected in sum by -1.8 μGal for: Coriolis -0.05 μgal , Verticality 0.6 μgal , Cable -0.57 μgal and fringe size correction: -1.85 μGal .

Remark to FG5-218: The transfer error to the height of the comparison of 1.25 m has no additional impact, as the same VGG was used. Due to a typo in Annex B the reported DA result had to be changed in May 25, 2022.

gravimeter	site	average Time	#drops	H	SAC	DC	g_{raw}	u_{raw}	VGG	dg_{ref}	udg_{ref}	SGC	σ_{SGC}	g	u
				/cm	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal·m ⁻¹	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal
FG5-242	FA	02.11.2021 23:02	990	122.0			68.63	2.40	-319.9	-9.60	0.03	0.62	0.09	59.65	2.41
FG5-242	DA	04.11.2021 02:12	898	122.0			51.34	2.50	-330.1	-9.90	0.03	-0.14	0.31	41.30	2.52
FG5-242	DA	04.11.2021 10:52	495	122.0			52.31	2.50	-330.1	-9.90	0.03	-0.99	0.07	41.42	2.51
FG5-242	EA	04.11.2021 22:58	1295	122.0			58.71	2.50	-319.5	-9.59	0.03	-0.72	0.10	48.41	2.51
FG5X-251H*	DA	07.09.2021 23:51	2550	127.022	-1.18	2.30	32.44	2.21	-330.1	6.67	0.02	-0.40	0.06	38.71	2.22
FG5X-251H*	CA	08.09.2021 20:21	2100	126.862	-1.18	2.30	44.33	2.22	-328.7	6.12	0.02	-0.13	0.08	50.32	2.23
AQG-A02	EA	08.10.2021 13:48	923694	55.8			274.63	7.50	-319.5	-221.09	0.62	-0.25	0.20	53.29	7.53
AQG-A02	FA	14.10.2021 18:41	153534	55.8			287.01	7.80	-319.9	-221.37	0.62	0.36	0.06	66.00	7.83
AQG-A02	CA	30.11.2021 03:52	65531	55.6			284.77	7.70	-328.7	-228.12	0.83	0.47	0.06	57.12	7.75
AQG-A02	DA	30.11.2021 14:02	52347	55.6			270.43	7.70	-330.1	-229.09	0.76	0.30	0.03	41.64	7.74
AQG-A02	FA	01.12.2021 01:39	86673	55.6			290.02	7.70	-319.9	-222.01	0.62	0.46	0.05	68.47	7.73
AQG-A02	EA	01.12.2021 19:48	135860	55.7			276.89	7.50	-319.5	-221.41	0.62	-0.33	0.36	55.15	7.53
AQG-B02	EA	13.11.2021 08:45	3890	63.9			240.29	8.00	-319.5	-195.21	0.55	-0.82	0.01	44.26	8.02
AQG-B02	EA	13.11.2021 09:29	3361	63.9			242.86	8.00	-319.5	-195.21	0.55	-0.85	0.02	46.80	8.02
AQG-B02	EA	13.11.2021 10:35	6853	63.9			234.97	8.00	-319.5	-195.21	0.55	-0.93	0.02	38.83	8.02
AQG-B02	FA	13.11.2021 12:13	10879	63.9			250.67	8.00	-319.9	-195.46	0.55	-0.99	0.03	54.22	8.02
AQG-B02	FA	13.11.2021 13:39	3387	64.2			239.36	8.00	-319.9	-194.50	0.55	-0.99	0.01	43.87	8.02
AQG-B02	CA	13.11.2021 14:54	10071	64.0			241.29	8.00	-328.7	-200.51	0.73	-1.00	0.01	39.78	8.04
AQG-B02	CA	13.11.2021 16:08	3444	63.9			247.68	8.00	-328.7	-200.84	0.73	-0.99	0.00	45.85	8.04
AQG-B02	EA	13.11.2021 17:22	9844	64.0			236.74	8.00	-319.5	-194.90	0.55	-0.98	0.01	40.87	8.02
AQG-B02	EA	13.11.2021 18:36	3354	64.0			240.25	8.00	-319.5	-194.90	0.55	-0.96	0.01	44.40	8.02
AQG-B02	FA	14.11.2021 01:39	83817	64.1			251.65	8.00	-319.9	-194.82	0.55	-1.03	0.04	55.80	8.02
AQG-B02	FA	14.11.2021 08:42	3657	64.1			245.49	8.00	-319.9	-194.82	0.55	-1.09	0.01	49.58	8.02
AQG-B02	CA	14.11.2021 09:59	10172	64.0			244.92	8.00	-328.7	-200.51	0.73	-1.15	0.02	43.26	8.04
AQG-B02	CA	14.11.2021 11:13	3360	64.0			249.77	8.00	-328.7	-200.51	0.73	-1.19	0.01	48.07	8.04

gravimeter	site	average Time	#Drops	H	SAC	DC	g_{raw}	u_{raw}	VGG	dg_{ref}	udg_{ref}	SGC	σ_{SGC}	g	u
				/cm	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal·m ⁻¹	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal
FG5-101	CA	12.10.2021 00:07	1500	122.0	-1.43	2.3	62.96	2.29	-328.7	-9.86	0.04	0.37	0.16	53.47	2.30
FG5-101	DA	12.10.2021 17:43	1200	122.0	-1.43	2.3	51.99	2.29	-330.1	-9.90	0.03	0.39	0.12	42.48	2.30
FG5-101	EA	14.10.2021 13:49	1000	122.0	-1.43	2.3	59.42	2.29	-319.5	-9.59	0.03	0.32	0.05	50.15	2.30
FG5-218	CA	01.11.2021 02:00	1440	100.0	-1.36	1.2	127.23	2.01	-328.7	-82.18	0.05	0.51	0.11	45.57	2.02
FG5-218	DA	02.11.2021 02:00	1440	100.0	-1.36	1.2	115.85	2.01	-330.1	-82.53	0.05	0.70	0.05	34.03	2.01
FG5-218	EA	03.11.2021 02:00	1440	100.0	-1.36	1.2	123.03	2.00	-319.5	-79.88	0.05	0.55	0.15	43.70	2.01
FG5-301	FA	01.11.2021 23:18	1200	122.0	-1.43	2.3	65.65	2.36	-319.9	-9.60	0.03	0.74	0.03	56.79	2.37
FG5-301	CA	04.11.2021 11:21	1100	122.0	-1.43	2.3	59.36	2.36	-328.7	-9.86	0.04	-0.97	0.09	48.53	2.37
FG5-301	DA	04.11.2021 20:34	1400	122.0	-1.43	2.3	48.09	2.36	-330.1	-9.90	0.03	-0.67	0.07	37.52	2.37
FG5X-220	EA	03.11.2021 13:53	1000	125.0			50.75	2.10	-319.5	0.00	0,00	0.15	0.06	50.90	2.11
FG5X-220	EA	03.11.2021 19:54	1000	125.0			51.66	2.10	-319.5	0.00	0,00	0.10	0.05	51.76	2.11
FG5X-220	FA	04.11.2021 11:28	500	125.0			60.36	2.10	-319.9	0.00	0,00	-0.95	0.03	59.41	2.11
FG5X-220	FA	04.11.2021 14:35	500	125.0			62.48	2.10	-319.9	0.00	0,00	-0.84	0.02	61.64	2.11
FG5X-220	CA	04.11.2021 19:23	1000	125.0			52.39	2.10	-328.7	0.00	0,00	-0.71	0.06	51.68	2.11
FG5X-233	FA	12.10.2021 00:08	2920	127.0	-1.20	1.00	50.26	2.40	-319.9	6.40	0.02	0.37	0.16	57.03	2.41
FG5X-233	CA	12.10.2021 21:31	3281	127.0	-1.20	1.00	40.34	2.40	-328.7	6.57	0.02	0.41	0.12	47.32	2.41
FG5X-233	DA	13.10.2021 10:36	1193	127.0	-1.20	1.00	31.76	2.40	-330.1	6.60	0.02	0.40	0.03	38.76	2.41
FG5X-233	EA	13.10.2021 22:14	3027	127.0	-1.20	1.00	37.51	2.40	-319.5	6.39	0.02	0.27	0.06	44.17	2.41

5. Measurement strategy

According to the Technical Protocol, four sites were used during the comparison. The first session took place from 7th to 9th of September 2021 and the last measurement was finished on 2nd of December 2021. Each gravimeter was planned to measure at least three sites, FG5X-251H occupied only two sites.

Table 5. Occupation of individual sites by gravimeters (x means one occupation, xxxxx means five reported occupations/setup). For FG5-242 DA measurement see remark to FG5-242 at table 4.

Gravimeter	Site				TOTAL
	CA	DA	EA	FA	
FG5-242		XX	X	X	3
FG5X-251H	x	x			2
Number of NMI/DI gravimeters	1	2	1	1	
AQG-A02	x	x	xx	xx	4
AQG-B02	xxxx		xxxxx	xxxx	3
FG5-101	x	x	x		3
FG5-218	x	x	x		3
FG5-301	x	x		x	3
FG5X-220	x		xx	xx	3
FG5X-233	x	x	x	x	4
Number of gravimeters occupying each site	8	7	7	6	

The pandemic situation didn't allow for a perfect tuning of the schedule. Thus, at least one gravimeter from NMI/DI and at least six gravimeters occupied each site.

Gravity variations during the comparison were measured with the superconducting gravimeter SG-030 at pillar G, see Figure 1. As it can be seen from Figure 2, the residual temporal gravity variations reach up to 2 μGal during the period of the comparison.

Figure 2. The residual gravity variations observed during the comparison with the superconducting gravimeter GWR SG-030 (gravity variations are referred to October 20, 2021 12:00 UT as the reference time of the comparison). Red dots mark the reference time of the reported absolute gravity observations.

These gravity variations were obtained from the SG signal of the lower sensor using the calibration factor of $-74.008 \mu\text{Gal}/\text{V}$ and accounting for the same corrections of temporal gravity variations as listed in Section 4 and Table 3, and an instrumental drift of $11.225 \mu\text{Gal}/\text{year}$.

6. Data elaboration

A combined (observation and constraint equations) least-squares adjustment was performed using the gravity values at the reference comparison height (g) and their associated uncertainties (u) as input. Every measurement made by the gravimeter " i " (with a bias δ_i) at the site " j " during the comparison may be described by the observation equation

$$g_{ij} = g_j + \delta_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

at respective weights w_{ij} ($w_{ij} = u_o^2/u_{ij}^2$ where u_o is the unit weight).

As the set of observation equations has no unique solution for δ , a constraint, which can be interpreted as definition of the CRV is required (Koo and Clare, 2012).

Generally, the consensus value of the CRV (Koo and Clare 2012) is obtained by including the weighted constraint

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \delta_i = d \quad (2)$$

where the w_i are the weights assigned indirect proportional to the mean uncertainty reported for each gravimeter, normalized by the condition $\sum w_i = 1$, and d is the linking converter (Jiang et al. 2013). The harmonized uncertainties (see below) were used for the determination of w_i .

Following Pálinkáš et al. (2021) two different solutions (ICN/KCN) were processed and shown in the next two chapters. Please see this paper for more details on the processing strategy. To the ICN solution all gravimeters contribute to the definition of reference values. There will be no link to other comparisons, thus $d = 0$. For this solution the reported data of FG5X-251H have been used without considering the bias to FG5-215H.

The KCN solution is considering only the group of gravimeters belonging to NMI/DIs for the definition of comparison reference values (CCM (2015)). Non-NMI/DI gravimeters cannot be included into the constraint nor in the determination of the linking converter d . Therefore, weights for non-NMI/DI gravimeters are all set to zero in Eq. (2). By this simple mathematical operation, this group of gravimeters is contributing only with gravity differences between the sites.

Harmonization of uncertainties

As proposed by Pálinkáš et al. (2021) declared uncertainties of those FG5/X gravimeters lower than $2.4 \mu\text{Gal}$ were changed to this value in the ICN solution. In case of the KCN solution, only the uncertainties of non-NMI/DIs were harmonized.

Linking converter

Table 6. Determination of the linking converters as weighted mean of DoE determined at the EURAMET.M.G-K3 (Falk et. al, 2020) and CCM.G-K2.2017 (Wu et al., 2020) of joint NMI/DI participants of the three comparisons. Due to the bias of $1.8 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{Gal}$ applied to FG5X-251H original measurements, these results are in the level of FG5-215 H

gravimeter	EURAMET.M.G-K3		CCM.G-K2.2017	
	DoE / μGal	u / μGal	DoE / μGal	u / μGal
FG5-242	-1.1	2.75	-0.1	3.45
FG5X-251H* /(FG5-215H)	-1.2	2.50	-1.0	2.25
linking converter d	-1.15	1.85	-0.73	1.88

7. ICN-solution

7.1 The initial approach and consistency check

For the initial ICN solution of the comparison, the measurements presented by the operators (Table 4, not considering the first FG5-242 measurement at DA, see comment at page 8) were included in a least-squares adjustment. The reference values (RVs) and the biases (δ) are presented in Table 7. This initial solution was computed based on Pálinkáš et.al. (2021), using the weighted constraint (Eq. 2) where the weights were computed as the normalized root mean square of the uncertainties (u) given in Table 4.

In Pálinkáš et al. 2021 it has been shown that underestimated uncertainties provided for some gravimeters should be harmonized. Such a harmonization also ensures more realistic weighting of the g -values in Eq. (1). Declared uncertainties of FG5/X gravimeters lower than the mean uncertainty declared for the NMI FG5/X gravimeter (2.40 μGal) (Pálinkáš et al. 2021) were set to this value.

A correlation of 0.75 was introduced for all AG. This includes the AQGs, as we found a similar ratio between uncertainty and repeatability as for the FG5/X.

The consistency of measurements was checked based on the reported uncertainties. The compatibility index is defined as the ratio between the difference of the measured gravity value (g_{ij}) and the RV (g_j) at a site and its uncertainty

$$E_{ij} = \frac{(g_{ij} - g_j)}{u(d_{ij})} \quad (3)$$

where the uncertainty of deviations $u(d_{ij})$ are achieved from error propagation accounting for correlations between observations (Pálinkáš et al. 2021).

In agreement with previous reports we have chosen the expanded uncertainty to compute the compatibility index. An absolute value of E_n larger than 2 indicates then that the measured gravity value is incompatible at a 95% confidence level, as the difference is not covered by the (expanded) uncertainties. The harmonized compatibility index $E_{n \text{ har}}$ is given in Table 7, using the harmonized uncertainties for the reported results.

The harmonized compatibility indexes except of one measurement of WET-CAG2021 are below 2, indicating consistency with the harmonized uncertainties. Only one observation of FG5-218 (DA) was found to be incompatible and the uncertainties of all measurements with this instrument were increased again by 50%.

Table 7. Reference Values (RVs) of the comparison using all the reported absolute measurements, reference height is 1.250 m. The constant value 980,836,900.0 μGal is subtracted from the RVs, σ is the standard deviation of RVs from the adjustment. Consistency check: Comparison of measured gravity values g_{ij} (along with declared and harmonized uncertainties u_{gij} , $u_{gij \text{ har}}$) with reference values g_j (along with standard deviations σ_{g_j}) by means of harmonized compatibility index $E_{n \text{ har}}$.

(Please consider, that for FG5X-251H the bias to FG5-215H by $1.8 \pm \mu\text{gal}$ was not applied for the ICN-solution.)

gravimeter	site	g_{ij}	u_{gij}	$u_{gij\ har}$	g_j	σ_{g_j}	δ	$E_{n\ har}$
		/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	
FG5-242	FA	59.65	2.41	2.41	58.18	0.97	1.47	0.7
FG5-242	DA	41.42	2.51	2.51	39.33	0.94	2.08	0.9
FG5-242	EA	48.40	2.51	2.51	47.71	0.95	0.69	0.3
FG5X-251H	DA	36.91	2.22	2.40	39.33	0.94	-2.42	-1.1
FG5X-251H	CA	48.52	2.23	2.40	49.88	0.93	-1.36	-0.6
AQG-A02	EA	53.29	7.53	7.53	47.71	0.95	5.57	0.7
AQG-A02	FA	66.00	7.83	7.83	58.18	0.97	7.81	1.0
AQG-A02	CA	57.12	7.75	7.75	49.88	0.93	7.24	0.9
AQG-A02	DA	41.64	7.74	7.74	39.33	0.94	2.31	0.3
AQG-A02	FA	68.47	7.73	7.73	58.18	0.97	10.28	1.3
AQG-A02	EA	55.15	7.53	7.53	47.71	0.95	7.43	1.0
AQG-B02	EA	44.26	8.02	8.02	47.71	0.95	-3.46	-0.4
AQG-B02	EA	46.80	8.02	8.02	47.71	0.95	-0.92	-0.1
AQG-B02	EA	38.83	8.02	8.02	47.71	0.95	-8.89	-1.1
AQG-B02	FA	54.22	8.02	8.02	58.18	0.97	-3.96	-0.5
AQG-B02	FA	43.87	8.02	8.02	58.18	0.97	-14.31	-1.8
AQG-B02	CA	39.78	8.04	8.04	49.88	0.93	-10.1	-1.3
AQG-B02	CA	45.85	8.04	8.04	49.88	0.93	-4.03	-0.5
AQG-B02	EA	40.87	8.02	8.02	47.71	0.95	-6.85	-0.9
AQG-B02	EA	44.40	8.02	8.02	47.71	0.95	-3.32	-0.4
AQG-B02	FA	55.80	8.02	8.02	58.18	0.97	-2.38	-0.3
AQG-B02	FA	49.58	8.02	8.02	58.18	0.97	-8.6	-1.1
AQG-B02	CA	43.26	8.04	8.04	49.88	0.93	-6.62	-0.8
AQG-B02	CA	48.07	8.04	8.04	49.88	0.93	-1.81	-0.2
FG5-101	CA	53.47	2.30	2.40	49.88	0.93	3.59	1.6
FG5-101	DA	42.48	2.30	2.40	39.33	0.94	3.14	1.4
FG5-101	EA	50.15	2.30	2.40	47.71	0.95	2.44	1.1
FG5-218	CA	45.56	2.02	2.40	49.88	0.93	-4.32	-1.8
FG5-218	DA	34.03	2.01	2.40	39.33	0.94	-5.31	-2.2
FG5-218	EA	43.70	2.01	2.40	47.71	0.95	-4.01	-1.7
FG5-301	FA	56.79	2.37	2.40	58.18	0.97	-1.39	-0.6
FG5-301	CA	48.53	2.37	2.40	49.88	0.93	-1.35	-0.6
FG5-301	DA	37.52	2.37	2.40	39.33	0.94	-1.82	-0.8
FG5X-220	EA	50.90	2.11	2.40	47.71	0.95	3.19	1.4
FG5X-220	EA	51.76	2.11	2.40	47.71	0.95	4.05	1.8
FG5X-220	FA	59.41	2.11	2.40	58.18	0.97	1.23	0.6
FG5X-220	FA	61.64	2.11	2.40	58.18	0.97	3.46	1.6
FG5X-220	CA	51.68	2.11	2.40	49.88	0.93	1.8	0.8
FG5X-233	FA	57.03	2.41	2.41	58.18	0.97	-1.16	-0.5
FG5X-233	CA	47.32	2.41	2.41	49.88	0.93	-2.56	-1.2
FG5X-233	DA	38.76	2.41	2.41	39.33	0.94	-0.57	-0.3
FG5X-233	EA	44.17	2.41	2.41	47.71	0.95	-3.54	-1.6

7.2 Final solution

The measurements of FG5- 218 have not been removed from the final solution, as they showed stable deviations, not affecting the gravity differences.

So, the RV of the initial solution (Table 7) is the same to the final ICN-RV (Table 8). The DoEs presented below are equivalent with the mean biases δ because no measurement had to be excluded.

The official *DoE* (cf. Table 12 and Figure 3) were computed according to Jiang et al. (2012) using the formula

$$D_i = \left[\sum w_{ij} (g_{ij} - g_j) \right] / \sum w_{ij}. \quad (4)$$

as the weighted average difference between the measurements of a gravimeter i and the CRV at site j . The differences between measurement and the ICN-RV are calculated for each gravimeter at each occupied site (column δ in Table 8). The *DoE* are then obtained by averaging these differences (according to Eq. 4 with weights proportional to $u_{Di,j}$) and its uncertainty is computed by error propagation, accounting for correlation (Pálinkáš et al 2021) and labeled u_{DoE} in Table 10.

The short-term reproducibility (Jiang et al. 2012) was also computed for each AG from the differences between each observation with the respective CRV as the standard deviation

$$R_i = \sqrt{\sum (g_{ij} - g_j)^2 / (n - 1)}. \quad (5)$$

It allows to assess whether an incompatibility is caused by systematic deviation of an instrument. The measurements of FG5-218 show with 0.7 μGal a high repeatability. Since its DoE exceeds significantly the (harmonized) uncertainty it was excluded from the constraint Eq. (2).

Table 8. ICN-solution Comparison Reference Values (ICN-RV). The constant value 980,836,900.0 μGal was subtracted from the ICN-RV. u is the uncertainty at 68.3% confidence level computed as root mean square of standard deviations σ (from the least-squares adjustment). The reference height is 1.250 m.

The ICN-RVs refer to October 20, 2021 12:00 UT as the mean time of the comparison.

ICN-SOLUTION RESULTS WET-CAG2021 COMPARISON			
Site	ICN-RV / μGal	σ / μGal	$u (k = 1)$ / μGal
CA	49.88	0.93	0.93
DA	39.33	0.94	0.94
EA	47.71	0.95	0.95
FA	58.18	0.97	0.97

Table 9. *DoE* of NMI/DIs determined according to Eq. 4.

g_{ij} are the measured gravity values transferred to 1.250 m with harmonized uncertainty $u_{ij \text{ har}}$.

g_j are the ICN-RVs with associated ($k = 1$) uncertainties u_j .

D_{ij} are the differences $g_{ij} - g_j$ with uncertainty u_{Dij}

D_i is the final ICN *DoE* computed according to Eq. 4 along with the uncertainty u_{Di} (computed from u_{Dij} values, considering correlation of D_{ij} values).

R_i is the reproducibility according to Eq. 5.

The constant value 980,836,900.0 μGal was subtracted from the gravity values.

gravimeter	site	g_{ij}	u_{ij} har	g_j	u_j	D_{ij}	u_{Dij}	D_i	u_{Di}	R_i
i	j	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal
FG5-242	FA	59.65	2.41	58.18	0.97	1.47	2.19	1.42	2.03	0.7
FG5-242	DA	41.42	2.51	39.33	0.94	2.08	2.29	1.42	2.03	0.7
FG5-242	EA	48.40	2.51	47.71	0.95	0.69	2.29	1.42	2.03	0.7
FG5X-251H	DA	36.91	2.40	39.33	0.94	-2.42	2.05	-1.89	1.93	0.8
FG5X-251H	CA	48.52	2.40	49.88	0.93	-1.36	2.06	-1.89	1.93	0.8
AQG-A02	EA	53.29	7.53	47.71	0.95	5.57	7.47	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-A02	FA	66.00	7.83	58.18	0.97	7.81	7.77	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-A02	CA	57.12	7.75	49.88	0.93	7.24	7.68	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-A02	DA	41.64	7.74	39.33	0.94	2.31	7.67	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-A02	FA	68.47	7.73	58.18	0.97	10.28	7.67	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-A02	EA	55.15	7.53	47.71	0.95	7.43	7.47	6.77	6.67	2.7
AQG-B02	EA	44.26	8.02	47.71	0.95	-3.46	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	46.80	8.02	47.71	0.95	-0.92	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	38.83	8.02	47.71	0.95	-8.89	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	54.22	8.02	58.18	0.97	-3.96	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	43.87	8.02	58.18	0.97	-14.31	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	39.78	8.04	49.88	0.93	-10.1	7.98	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	45.85	8.04	49.88	0.93	-4.03	7.98	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	40.87	8.02	47.71	0.95	-6.85	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	44.40	8.02	47.71	0.95	-3.32	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	55.80	8.02	58.18	0.97	-2.38	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	49.58	8.02	58.18	0.97	-8.6	7.97	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	43.26	8.04	49.88	0.93	-6.62	7.98	-5.79	6.99	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	48.07	8.04	49.88	0.93	-1.81	7.98	-5.79	6.99	3.9
FG5-101	CA	53.47	2.40	49.88	0.93	3.59	2.11	3.06	1.93	0.6
FG5-101	DA	42.48	2.40	39.33	0.94	3.14	2.11	3.06	1.93	0.6
FG5-101	EA	50.15	2.40	47.71	0.95	2.44	2.11	3.06	1.93	0.6
FG5-218	CA	45.56	2.40	49.88	0.93	-4.32	2.05	-4.55	1.89	0.7
FG5-218	DA	34.03	2.40	39.33	0.94	-5.31	2.04	-4.55	1.89	0.7
FG5-218	EA	43.70	2.40	47.71	0.95	-4.01	2.04	-4.55	1.89	0.7
FG5-301	FA	56.79	2.40	58.18	0.97	-1.39	2.15	-1.52	1.98	0.3
FG5-301	CA	48.53	2.40	49.88	0.93	-1.35	2.16	-1.52	1.98	0.3
FG5-301	DA	37.52	2.40	39.33	0.94	-1.82	2.16	-1.52	1.98	0.3
FG5X-220	EA	50.90	2.40	47.71	0.95	3.19	1.99	2.74	1.78	1.2
FG5X-220	EA	51.76	2.40	47.71	0.95	4.05	1.99	2.74	1.78	1.2
FG5X-220	FA	59.41	2.40	58.18	0.97	1.23	1.99	2.74	1.78	1.2
FG5X-220	FA	61.64	2.40	58.18	0.97	3.46	1.99	2.74	1.78	1.2
FG5X-220	CA	51.68	2.40	49.88	0.93	1.8	1.97	2.74	1.78	1.2
FG5X-233	FA	57.03	2.41	58.18	0.97	-1.16	2.19	-1.96	1.98	1.3
FG5X-233	CA	47.32	2.41	49.88	0.93	-2.56	2.2	-1.96	1.98	1.3
FG5X-233	DA	38.76	2.41	39.33	0.94	-0.57	2.19	-1.96	1.98	1.3
FG5X-233	EA	44.17	2.41	47.71	0.95	-3.54	2.19	-1.96	1.98	1.3

The final DoE with standard uncertainty at the 68.3% confidence level is presented in Tab. 10 and Fig. 3. All the gravimeters participating at WET-CAG2021 comparison are in equivalence.

Table 10. Degrees of Equivalence (*DoE*) for solution ICN of the gravimeters participating in the WET-CAG2021. The standard uncertainty u_{DoE} is obtained from error propagation considering correlation (68.3% confidence level).

ICN-SOLUTION RESULTS WET-CAG2021 COMPARISON		
gravimeter	Degree of Equivalence	
	<i>DoE</i> /μGal	u_{DoE} ($k = 1$) /μGal
FG5-242	1.42	2.03
FG5X-251H	-1.89	1.93
AQG-A02	6.77	6.67
AQG-B02	-5.79	6.99
FG5-101	3.06	1.93
FG5-218	-4.55	1.89
FG5-301	-1.52	1.98
FG5X-220	2.74	1.78
FG5X-233	-1.96	1.98

Figure 3. Degrees of Equivalence (*DoE*) in μGal of the gravimeters participating in the WET-CA2021 Comparison calculated from the difference between the gravimeter measurements and the CRV for the correspondent pillar. The error bars represent the standard uncertainties (U_{DoE}) of the *DoE* at 68.3% confidence. The DoEs are identical with the mean biases estimated from least square (labelled as LS) because no measurement became excluded. The incompatibility of FG5-218 with its DoE has been solved by down weighting in the constraint.

8. KCN-solution

8.1 The initial approach and consistency check

For the initial KCN solution, the measurements presented by the operators (Table 4, not considering the first FG5-242 measurement at DA, see comment at page 8) were included in a least-squares adjustment. The reference values (RVs) and the biases (δ) are presented in Table 11. This initial solution was computed based on Pálinkáš et.al. (2021), using the weighted constraint (Eq. 2) where the weights were computed as the normalized root mean square of the uncertainties (u) given in Table 4. Thus, the values 0.54 for FG5X-251H and 0.46 for FG5-242 are obtained. The sum of these weights is equal to 1 to ensure the correct scaling of the linking converter (Tab.6). The weights of the other non NMI/DI gravimeters of the WET-CAG2021 have been set to zero in Eq. (2).

As for the ICN solution underestimated uncertainties were harmonized and declared uncertainties of non-NMI/DI FG5/X gravimeters lower than the mean uncertainty for the NMI/DI FG5/X gravimeter (2.40 μ Gal) were set to this value.

Table 11. Reference Values (RVs) of the comparison using all the reported absolute measurements, reference height is 1.250 m. Results are linked by 4 instruments from NMI/DI to EURAMET.M.G-K3 by means of linking converter (Table 6). The constant value 980,836,900.0 μ Gal is subtracted from the RVs, σ is the standard deviation of RVs from the adjustment. Results of FG5X-251H in the KCN- solution contain an offset of (1.80 \pm 0.3) μ gal to FG5-215H, which participated at CCM.G.K2.2017, so the instrument is labelled FG5X-251H*.

gravimeter	site	g	u_g	u_g _{har}	g _{adj}	u_g _{adj}	res	KCN-RV, g _i	σ	δ	E _{n har}
		/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	/ μ Gal	
FG5-242	FA	59.65	2.41	2.41	59.61	2.26	0.04	59.94	2.45	-0.28	-0.1
FG5-242	DA	41.42	2.51	2.51	40.74	2.27	0.67	41.07	2.42	0.35	0.1
FG5-242	EA	48.40	2.51	2.51	49.14	2.26	-0.73	49.46	2.45	-1.06	-0.4
FG5X-251H*	DA	38.71	2.22	2.22	39.22	2.11	-0.51	41.07	2.42	-2.36	-1.0
FG5X-251H*	CA	50.32	2.23	2.23	49.8	2.11	0.52	51.65	2.43	-1.33	-0.5
AQG-A02	EA	53.29	7.53	7.53	54.46	6.74	-1.18	49.46	2.45	3.82	0.5
AQG-A02	FA	66.00	7.83	7.83	64.93	6.74	1.06	59.94	2.45	6.06	0.7
AQG-A02	CA	57.12	7.75	7.75	56.65	6.74	0.48	51.65	2.43	5.48	0.7
AQG-A02	DA	41.64	7.74	7.74	46.07	6.75	-4.43	41.07	2.42	0.57	0.1
AQG-A02	FA	68.47	7.73	7.73	64.93	6.74	3.53	59.94	2.45	8.53	1.1
AQG-A02	EA	55.15	7.53	7.53	54.46	6.74	0.68	49.46	2.45	5.68	0.7
AQG-B02	EA	44.26	8.02	8.02	41.92	7.05	2.34	49.46	2.45	-5.21	-0.6
AQG-B02	EA	46.80	8.02	8.02	41.92	7.05	4.88	49.46	2.45	-2.67	-0.3
AQG-B02	EA	38.83	8.02	8.02	41.92	7.05	-3.09	49.46	2.45	-10.64	-1.3
AQG-B02	FA	54.22	8.02	8.02	52.39	7.05	1.83	59.94	2.45	-5.71	-0.7
AQG-B02	FA	43.87	8.02	8.02	52.39	7.05	-8.52	59.94	2.45	-16.06	-1.9
AQG-B02	CA	39.78	8.04	8.04	44.1	7.05	-4.32	51.65	2.43	-11.86	-1.4
AQG-B02	CA	45.85	8.04	8.04	44.1	7.05	1.75	51.65	2.43	-5.79	-0.7
AQG-B02	EA	40.87	8.02	8.02	41.92	7.05	-1.06	49.46	2.45	-8.60	-1.0
AQG-B02	EA	44.4	8.02	8.02	41.92	7.05	2.47	49.46	2.45	-5.07	-0.6
AQG-B02	FA	55.80	8.02	8.02	52.39	7.05	3.41	59.94	2.45	-4.13	-0.5
AQG-B02	FA	49.58	8.02	8.02	52.39	7.05	-2.81	59.94	2.45	-10.35	-1.2
AQG-B02	CA	43.26	8.04	8.04	44.1	7.05	-0.84	51.65	2.43	-8.38	-1.0
AQG-B02	CA	48.07	8.04	8.04	44.1	7.05	3.97	51.65	2.43	-3.57	-0.4

FG5-101	CA	53.47	2.3	2.4	52.95	2.23	0.52	51.65	2.43	1.82	0.5
FG5-101	DA	42.48	2.3	2.4	42.38	2.23	0.10	41.07	2.42	1.41	0.4
FG5-101	EA	50.15	2.3	2.4	50.77	2.23	-0.62	49.46	2.45	0.69	0.2
FG5-218	CA	45.56	2.02	2.4	45.35	2.23	0.21	51.65	2.43	-6.08	-1.8
FG5-218	DA	34.03	2.01	2.4	34.78	2.23	-0.75	41.07	2.42	-7.04	-2.1
FG5-218	EA	43.70	2.01	2.4	43.17	2.23	0.54	49.46	2.45	-5.76	-1.7
FG5-301	FA	56.79	2.37	2.4	56.66	2.24	0.13	59.94	2.45	-3.14	-0.9
FG5-301	CA	48.53	2.37	2.4	48.38	2.23	0.15	51.65	2.43	-3.12	-0.9
FG5-301	DA	37.52	2.37	2.4	37.8	2.23	-0.28	41.07	2.42	-3.55	-1.1
FG5X-220	EA	50.90	2.11	2.4	50.45	2.18	0.45	49.46	2.45	1.44	0.4
FG5X-220	EA	51.76	2.11	2.4	50.45	2.18	1.31	49.46	2.45	2.30	0.7
FG5X-220	FA	59.41	2.11	2.4	60.92	2.18	-1.51	59.94	2.45	-0.53	-0.2
FG5X-220	FA	61.64	2.11	2.4	60.92	2.18	0.72	59.94	2.45	1.70	0.5
FG5X-220	CA	51.68	2.11	2.4	52.63	2.21	-0.95	51.65	2.43	0.03	0.0
FG5X-233	FA	57.03	2.41	2.41	56.23	2.22	0.8	59.94	2.45	-2.91	-0.9
FG5X-233	CA	47.32	2.41	2.41	47.94	2.21	-0.61	51.65	2.43	-4.32	-1.3
FG5X-233	DA	38.76	2.41	2.41	37.36	2.22	1.4	41.07	2.42	-2.31	-0.7
FG5X-233	EA	44.17	2.41	2.41	45.76	2.22	-1.59	49.46	2.45	-5.29	-1.6

The harmonized compatibility indexes except of one measurement are below 2, indicating consistency with the harmonized uncertainties. One measurement of FG5-218 (DA) was found to be incompatible and the uncertainties of all measurements with this instrument were increased again by 50%.

Table 12. KCN-solution Comparison Reference Values linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3 using linking converter of $(-1.15 \pm 1.85) \mu\text{Gal}$ and also to CCM.G-K2.2017 using linking converter of $(-0.73 \pm 1.88) \mu\text{Gal}$ related to 2 NMI/DI gravimeters. The constant value 980,836,900.0 μGal was subtracted from the KCN-RV. u is the uncertainty at 68.3% confidence level computed as root mean square of standard deviations σ (from the least-squares adjustment) and the uncertainty of the linking converter. The reference height is 1.250 m. The KCN-RVs refer to October 20, 2021 12:00 UT as the mean time of the comparison.

KCN-SOLUTION RESULTS WET-CAG2021 COMPARISON						
site	linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3 in 2018			linked to CCM.G-K2.2017		
	KCN-RV / μGal	σ / μGal	$u (k = 1)$ / μGal	KCN-RV / μGal	σ / μGal	$u (k = 1)$ / μGal
CA	51.65	1.58	2.43	51.23	1.58	2.45
DA	41.07	1.56	2.42	40.65	1.56	2.44
EA	49.46	1.60	2.45	49.04	1.60	2.47
FA	59.94	1.61	2.45	59.52	1.61	2.48

Table 13. *DoE* of NMI/DIs determined according to Eq. 4.

g_{ij} are the measured gravity values transferred to 1.250 m with uncertainty u_{ij} .

g_j are the KN-RVs with associated ($k = 1$) uncertainties u_j , using the link to EURAMET.M.G-K3

D_{ij} are the differences $g_{ij} - g_j$ with uncertainty u_{Dij}

u_{Dij} is the uncertainty of differences $g_{ij} - g_j$.

D_i is the final *DoE* computed according to Eq. 4 along with the uncertainty u_{Di} (computed from u_{Dij} values, assuming statistical independence of D_{ij} values). R_i is the reproducibility according to Eq. 5.

The constant value 980,836,900.0 μGal was subtracted from the gravity values.

gravimeter	site	g_{ij}	$u_{ij \text{ har}}$	g_j	u_j	D_{ij}	u_{Dij}	D_i	u_{Di}	R_i
i	j	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal	/μGal
FG5-242	FA	59.65	2.41	59.94	2.45	-0.28	2.62	-0.33	1.66	0.7
FG5-242	DA	41.42	2.51	41.07	2.42	0.35	2.7	-0.33	1.66	0.7
FG5-242	EA	48.40	2.51	49.46	2.45	-1.06	2.7	-0.33	1.66	0.7
FG5X-251H*	DA	38.71	2.22	41.07	2.42	-2.36	2.43	-1.84	1.41	0.7
FG5X-251H*	CA	50.32	2.23	51.65	2.43	-1.33	2.43	-1.84	1.41	0.7
AQG-A02	EA	53.29	7.53	49.46	2.45	3.82	7.89	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-A02	FA	66.00	7.83	59.94	2.45	6.06	8.17	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-A02	CA	57.12	7.75	51.65	2.43	5.48	8.10	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-A02	DA	41.64	7.74	41.07	2.42	0.57	8.09	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-A02	FA	68.47	7.73	59.94	2.45	8.53	8.08	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-A02	EA	55.15	7.53	49.46	2.45	5.68	7.89	5.02	6.90	2.7
AQG-B02	EA	44.26	8.02	49.46	2.45	-5.21	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	46.80	8.02	49.46	2.45	-2.67	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	38.83	8.02	49.46	2.45	-10.64	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	54.22	8.02	59.94	2.45	-5.71	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	43.87	8.02	59.94	2.45	-16.06	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	39.78	8.04	51.65	2.43	-11.86	8.38	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	45.85	8.04	51.65	2.43	-5.79	8.38	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	40.87	8.02	49.46	2.45	-8.60	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	EA	44.40	8.02	49.46	2.45	-5.07	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	55.80	8.02	59.94	2.45	-4.13	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	FA	49.58	8.02	59.94	2.45	-10.35	8.36	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	43.26	8.04	51.65	2.43	-8.38	8.38	-7.54	7.20	3.9
AQG-B02	CA	48.07	8.04	51.65	2.43	-3.57	8.38	-7.54	7.20	3.9
FG5-101	CA	53.47	2.40	51.65	2.43	1.82	3.30	1.31	2.59	0.6
FG5-101	DA	42.48	2.40	41.07	2.42	1.41	3.30	1.31	2.59	0.6
FG5-101	EA	50.15	2.40	49.46	2.45	0.69	3.29	1.31	2.59	0.6
FG5-218	CA	45.56	2.40	51.65	2.43	-6.08	3.12	-6.30	2.39	0.7
FG5-218	DA	34.03	2.40	41.07	2.42	-7.04	3.11	-6.30	2.39	0.7
FG5-218	EA	43.70	2.40	49.46	2.45	-5.76	3.11	-6.30	2.39	0.7
FG5-301	FA	56.79	2.40	59.94	2.45	-3.14	3.34	-3.27	2.64	0.2
FG5-301	CA	48.53	2.40	51.65	2.43	-3.12	3.34	-3.27	2.64	0.2
FG5-301	DA	37.52	2.40	41.07	2.42	-3.55	3.34	-3.27	2.64	0.2
FG5X-220	EA	50.90	2.40	49.46	2.45	1.44	3.19	0.99	2.44	1.2
FG5X-220	EA	51.76	2.40	49.46	2.45	2.30	3.19	0.99	2.44	1.2
FG5X-220	FA	59.41	2.40	59.94	2.45	-0.53	3.19	0.99	2.44	1.2
FG5X-220	FA	61.64	2.40	59.94	2.45	1.70	3.19	0.99	2.44	1.2
FG5X-220	CA	51.68	2.40	51.65	2.43	0.03	3.17	0.99	2.44	1.2
FG5X-233	FA	57.03	2.41	59.94	2.45	-2.91	3.36	-3.71	2.65	1.3
FG5X-233	CA	47.32	2.41	51.65	2.43	-4.32	3.37	-3.71	2.65	1.3
FG5X-233	DA	38.76	2.41	41.07	2.42	-2.31	3.36	-3.71	2.65	1.3
FG5X-233	EA	44.17	2.41	49.46	2.45	-5.29	3.36	-3.71	2.65	1.3

The final *DoE* with uncertainty at the 68.3 % confidence level are presented in Table 14 and Figure 4.

Table 14. Degrees of Equivalence (*DoE*) for solution KCN of the gravimeters participating in WET-CAG2021. The standard uncertainty u_{DoE} is obtained from error propagation considering correlation (68.3% confidence level). FG5-251H* is given in the level of FG5-215H. Results using different links (Tab.6) are presented.

KCN-SOLUTION RESULTS WET-CAG2021 COMPARISON				
gravimeter	Degree of Equivalence linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3 in 2018		Degree of Equivalence linked to CCM.G-K2.2017	
	<i>DoE</i> /μGal	u_{DoE} (<i>k</i> = 1) /μGal	<i>DoE</i> /μGal	u_{DoE} (<i>k</i> = 1) /μGal
FG5-242	-0.33	1.66	0.09	1.66
FG5X-251H*	-1.84	1.41	-1.42	1.41
AQG-A02	5.02	6.90	5.44	6.90
AQG-B02	-7.54	7.20	-7.12	7.20
FG5-101	1.31	2.59	1.73	2.59
FG5-218	-6.30	2.39	-5.88	2.39
FG5-301	-3.27	2.64	-2.85	2.64
FG5X-220	0.99	2.44	1.41	2.44
FG5X-233	-3.71	2.65	-3.29	2.65

Figure 4. Degrees of Equivalence (*DoE*) of the gravimeters participating in WET-CAG2021 calculated from the difference between the gravimeter measurements and the KCN-RV for the correspondent pillar. The error bars represent the standard uncertainties (u_{DoE}) of the *DoE* at 68.3 % confidence. These results are linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3.

9. Results and conclusion

The aim of the Additional comparison WET-CAG2021 was to check the long term stability of the FG5/X in relation to EURAMET.M.G-K3 and CCM.G-K2.2017, so and also to evaluate two new Quantum gravimeters.

Altogether nine gravimeters were compared within the framework WET-CAG2021. Two gravimeters were operated by NMI and DI, FG5-242 participated at EURAMET.M.G-K3 key comparison, FG5X-251H* was linked to FG5-215H, which also participated at EURAMET.M.G-K3 key comparison. So FG5-242 and FG5X-251H* were used to link WET-CAG2021 comparison to the EURAMET.M.G-K3 by means of the linking converter computed as weighted average of *DoE* as documented in Wu et al. (2020) for those gravimeters.

In conclusion, the ICN-solution *DoE* of the 2 NMI / DI gravimeters are within the range of -1.9 μGal and 1.4 μGal . For the other gravimeters participating in the WET-CAG2021 comparison the *DoE* are between -5.8 μGal and +6.8 μGal .

In conclusion, the both versions of the KCN-solution using different links differ by 0.42 μGal , where the link to EURAMET.M.G-K3 results in higher KCV and lower *DoE*. The *DoE* of the 2 NMI / DI gravimeters using the link to EURAMET.M.G-K3 are within the range of -1.8 μGal and -0.3 μGal . For the other gravimeters participating in the WET-CAG2021 comparison gravimeters using the link to EURAMET.M.G-K3 the *DoE* are between -7.5 μGal and +5.0 μGal .

Eight gravimeters participating in WET-CAG2021 Comparison are in both solutions in equivalence. FG5-218 shows high short-term reproducibility, but the determined *DoE* is not within the double of its declared and even the simple harmonized uncertainties.

Changes in some parts of FG5/X after earlier comparisons as other collimators or different fringe cables will lead to different corrections and need to be investigated and considered as corrections.

It is obvious, that comparison reference values with an accuracy of better than 1 μgal ($k=1$) are at present only to obtain with carefully investigation of all instrumental corrections of all participating instruments and in case of the KCN-solution by a linking converter with high accuracy.

For future comparisons it is recommended to change Annex B of the Technical Protocol. Only applied corrections should be reported.

It is obvious that the *DoE* of the FG5-101, FG5-301 and FG5X-220 have changed between 2021 and 2018 (Figure 5). Reasons can be found in instrumental changes, as the exchange of micro-g collimator to a Thorlabs collimator. Some additional instrumental corrections were applied in 2021 for FG5-101 and FG-301, which require further investigation.

For the NMI/DI instruments and also for FG5X-233 and FG5-218 a good long-term stability could be shown. For FG5/X the short-term reproducibility varies between 0.2 to 1.3 μGal .

Figure 5. Joint presentation of the Degrees of equivalence of the Additional Comparison of EURAMET.M.G-K3 and of the KCN-solution (linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3) of WET-CAG2021

Comparing the Comparison Reference values of 2018 and 2021 for the station Wettzell (Tab. 15) we can conclude, that only non-significant gravity changes between both mean comparison dates could be determined. Also, the gravity differences between the 4 measurement sites determined by both comparisons found to be stable. Comparing the KCN 2021 solution reference values with it of EURAMET.M.G-K3 we found no significant changes of the gravity differences between the 4 stations, in mean of -0.6 µGal, whereby differences related to station CA stands out with 1.1 µgal.

The ICN solution (here FG5X-251H was used without the bias the FG5-215H) show 1.8 µGal lower comparison reference values as the KCN solution. The KCN solution was determined using FG5X-251H*, which is considering also the bias of 1.8 µGal between FG5X-251H and FG5-215H representing the link to EURAMET.M.G-K3 comparison.

Table 15. Comparison of the KCRV of EURAMET.M.G-K3 and the CRVs of ICN and KCN (linked to EURAMET.M.G-K3) solutions of WET-CAG2021 and also comparison of the corresponding gravity differences between the four measurement sites.

site	KCN 2018 May 15, 2018 0:00 UT	u	KCN 2021 Oct. 20, 2021 12:00 UT	u	KCN2021-KCN2018 dg	u	ICN 2021 Oct. 20, 2021 12:00 UT	u	ICN2021-KCN2018 dg	u	KCN2021-ICN2021 dg	u
Comparison Reference values in µGal (reduced by 980 936 900 µGal)												
CA	52.8	1.4	51.7	2,43	-1.2	2.8	49.9	0.93	-2.9	1.6	1.8	2.6
DA	41.3	1.3	41.1	2,42	-0.2	2.7	39.3	0.94	-2.0	1.6	1.7	2.6
EA	49.6	1.4	49.5	2,45	-0.1	2.8	47.7	0.95	-1.9	1.7	1.8	2.6
FA	59.9	1.4	59.9	2,45	0.0	2.8	58.2	0.97	-1.7	1.7	1.8	2.6
				mean	-0.4			mean	-2.1		mean	1.8
gravity differences between the sites in µgal												
CA - DA	11.5	1.9	10.6	3.4	0.9	3.9	10.6	1.3	0.9	2.3	0.0	3.7
CA - EA	3.2	1.9	2.2	3.5	1.0	3.9	2.2	1.3	1.0	2.3	0.0	3.7
CA - FA	-7.1	1.9	-8.3	3.5	1.2	3.9	-8.3	1.3	1.2	2.3	0.0	3.7
DA - EA	-8.3	1.9	-8.4	3.4	0.1	3.9	-8.4	1.3	0.1	2.3	0.0	3.7
DA - FA	-18.6	1.9	-18.9	3.4	0.3	3.9	-18.9	1.4	0.3	2.3	0.0	3.7
EA - FA	-10.3	1.9	-10.5	3.5	0.2	4.0	-10.5	1.4	0.2	2.3	0.0	3.7

In future comparisons the handling of the additional instrumental corrections should give more attention. Not applied corrections in the past should be investigated and should increase the error budget by ignoring it.

Remarks to the AQGs:

For both AQG the compatibility indexes are below 2 indicating consistency with the declared uncertainties at a 95 % level of confidence. The AQGs short-term reproducibility is lower than the half of the declared uncertainties, also.

The reported measurement results of the AQGs (see Tab.4) have changed in the meantime due to a new characterization of the instruments by the manufacturer. The declared uncertainties were extended to about 11 μgal , also. In this report the new reprocessed AQG measurement results following the latest characterizations are not included.

10. References

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